

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF HEALTHCARE IN INDIA - OPPORTUNITIES, CHALLENGES, AND PATHWAYS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The eventual development of an economy depends upon the usage of level of technology. An improved technology in a country will have a great potential to become developed country. Hence Indian Government introduced the concept called Digital India where the Traditional doing things are digitally transforming in all sectors. The digital transformation refers to the process of using digital technologies in business processes, culture, customer requirements in order to cope up with the changing business and market requirements. Digital transformation has the latent to ensure customer service quality, accessibility, availability, affordability and equality. Health care sector is not the exception to this trend of digital transformation. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW) promoting digital health or e-health through Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to improve the delivery of healthcare services and management of public health systems. The recent National Health Policy, 2017 envisaged extensive deployment of digital tools for improving the efficiency and outcome of health care system and also intending to strengthen the health surveillance system and to establish country-wide health information exchange network by 2025. This paper aims to explore the present opportunities and challenges of digital transformation of healthcare sector for sustainable development in India. The present study is based on the conceptual framework.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, Healthcare Sector, Digital Health, E-health, Information and Communication Technology, National Health Policy, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW), Sustainable Development.

Cite this Article: Venkatesh Bathala, Y. Subbarayudu. Digital Transformation of Healthcare in India - Opportunities, Challenges, and Pathways for Sustainable Development. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(4), 2024, 221–227.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJM/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_4/IJM_15_04_017.pdf

1. Introduction

Digital transformation in recent years has been emerging as a strategic phenomenon in developing countries (Bharadwaj et al. 2013; Piccinini et al. 2015). Digital transformation encompasses the profound changes happening in society and industries with digital technologies (Agarwal et al. 2010; Majchrzak et al. 2016). Modern digital technologies, services and systems are extremely significant for the social development (Morze and Strutynska, 2021) and drives the better operational performance of the business (Hess et al. 2016). Digital transformation refers to the process that aims to improve an entity viz business, society, economy, etc by triggering significant changes to its properties through combination of information, computing, communication, and connectivity technologies.

The importance of digital transformation had increased, as it is addressing much more than the technological shifts (Sascha, k et al. 2021). Digitalization resulted by digital transformation provides the improvements in productivity, cost reductions, and innovations (Hess et al. 2016). According to a study conducted by Massachusetts Institute of Technology, digitally transformed businesses are 26% profitable than the traditional one and ensures the growth and creation of jobs in the economy. The phenomenon of globalization, changes in customer needs and requirements, facing fierce competition to survive and gain competitive advantage; digital transformation becomes essential and vital (Capusneanu, S et al. 2021) for all the sectors in an economy. Healthcare sector is not an exception to this digitalization trend.

The digital transformation of healthcare sector is a complex process and a multi sided phenomenon of characteristics like e-health, mobile health, health apps, e-patient communities, electronic medical records, etc. The digital transformation has reached healthcare sector and is changing closed systems into open, participative, flexible, and innovative healthcare networks (Bellinger and Krieger, 2016). There are significant issues like privacy and data security problems which have been resolved legally and technically and that takes into implementation in healthcare (Bellinger and Krieger, 2018). It could be a keystone for a successful reform of healthcare systems for improved efficiency and effectiveness for the benefit of the people (Alam et al. 2020). It creates exciting and new possibilities for medical services in rural areas, which are experiencing growth and renewal (Alami et al. 2017).

Indian economy's critical part is healthcare and digital transformation contributes the improvement of medical services, one of the goals of sustainable development goals. In addition, economic performance and health performance are interlinked. Thus providing affordable, accessible, equal and adequate health services are challenging because of the poor health infrastructure and high rate of density of population. In order to solve those problems, the Indian government launched Digital India initiative on July, 2015 to empower the country to become more digitally advanced by encompassing the establishment of secure and stable digital infrastructure, delivery of digital services, and ensuring that every citizen has access to the internet facilities. The intention is to forecast the benefits of all sectors including the core sectors like Healthcare, Information Technology, Business Process Management, Electronics and Manufacturing, etc are likely to double their GDP's to US\$ 355-435 billion by 2025. It is also expected to boost up the digital economy to US\$ 1 trillion by 2025. The digital health market is stood at \$ 86.4 billion in 2018 and is expected to reach \$ 500 billion by 2025 at a compounded annual growth rate of 26.9%. The recent studies had focused only on e-governance and telemedicine. But there is no investigation of current status of digital transformation of

healthcare sector in India. The present study gives the current status of digital transformation of healthcare sector in India.

2. Healthcare and Wellness Initiatives Developed Under Digital India

2.1 E-health

E-health provides interaction setting between healthcare providers and patients through electronic means, and timely and effective healthcare services like online registrations, payments, reports and claims.

2.2 Telemedicine

Telemedicine is the remote delivery of healthcare services including exams and consultations using telecommunication services.

2.3 Ayush Information Hub (AIH)

Ayush Information Hub provides information regarding traditional medicines and methods about Ayurveda Yoga, Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, Sowa – Rigpa, and Homeopathy.

2.4 DigiDrishti

DigiDrishti is a digital India initiative developed to promote digital eyecare delivery system.

2.5 Poshan Tracker

Poshan Tracker identifies stunting, wasting, and under-weight prevalence among children and ensure last-mile tracking of nutrition service delivery.

2.6 Esanjeevani

Esanjeevani is a digital India initiative, which is a cloud-based telemedicine platform.

2.7 Nextgen eHospital

Nextgen eHospital ensure seamless interoperability and data exchange among healthcare providers.

2.8 Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission

Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission provides digital health solutions of hospitals across the country.

2.9 Aarogya Setu

Aarogya Setu provides interaction with participating healthcare providers, and receive the digital lab reports, prescriptions and diagnosis seamlessly from verified healthcare professionals and health service providers.

2.10 Mhealth

Mobile health refers to the practice of medicine and welfare support using smart phones. Mhealth is one aspect of E-health pushed to deliver meaningful results.

2.11 Mera Aspatal

Mera Aspatal is a patient feedback system to improve hospitals system.

2.12 E-blood bank

E-blood bank facility provides the implementation of a complete blood bank management system.

2.13 Electronic Health Records (EHR)

Electronic Health Records is the systemized collection of patient records stored electronically to access at anytime and at anywhere.

2.14 Wearable sensors

Wearable sensors are the health monitors used to track the functioning of an individual body like heart rate, oxygen levels, etc.

2.15 Online Registration System (ORS)

Online Registration System is a framework to link various hospitals for online registration, appointment, payment of fee, availability of blood, etc. and it is integrated with Ayushman Bharat Health Account (ABHA).

3. Current Status of Digital Transformation of Health Care Through E-Hospital

E-hospital is offered as an as-is product to the government hospitals across the country offering different modules like Patient Registration (OPD, Causality, Appointment and ORS), IPD (Admission, Discharge and Transfer), Billing, Clinic (OPD and IPD), Lab Information System (LIS), Radiology Information System (RIS), Dietary, Laundry, Store and Pharmacy, OT Management, and Queue Management Mobile App.

Table 3.1: E-hospital dashboard (As on: 14-12-2024 05:00 PM)

Description	Active Number
Active hospitals	747
Patient registration	46,55,03,470
Admission	3,66,80,070
Prescription	73,15,243
Laboratory report	1,73,84,561
Radiology report	5,22,552
Discharge summary	1,49,87,450
ABHA created	20,71,236
Health record link request	2,58,58,734
Total teleconsultation	94,298
Total online appointments	1,06,01,018
Total Billing and Inventory	9,43,61,704

Source: <https://dashboard.ehospital.gov.in/ehospitaldashboard/>

4. Challenges of Digital Transformation in Health Care Sector

Challenges	Description	Reference
Regulatory Roadblock	Lack of clarity in advancing the program.	Bidisha Borah, 2020
Idle Government Request for Proposals (RFP's)	Due to Lack of Commercial Viability, Private Organizations are not accepting the RFP's Proposals issued by Government.	Bidisha Borah, 2020
Digital Divide	Differentiating the Digitally Equipped and Unequipped.	Bidisha Borah, 2020
Internet of Things	Devices using IOT cause harm, theft and unauthorized use of personal data	Smagulov, S & Smagulov, V 2019
Poor Connectivity	As of now, 31,000 Hotspots are covering for Digital Services in place of 80 Lakhs.	Bidisha Borah, 2020
Proper Policy Making	Policy is not made Properly to Implement.	Bidisha Borah, 2020
Digital Literacy	Digital Literacy is very challenging in India.	Bidisha Borah, 2020
Slow and Delayed Infrastructure Development	Inadequate Digital Infrastructure is used to tackle the growing transactions.	Bidisha Borah, 2020 Smagulov, S & Smagulov, V 2019
Non-availability of Data in own Language	India has different Languages and the Digital Services is not available in all Languages.	Bidisha Borah, 2020
Cyber Crime and Breach of Privacy	Indian People have the Fear of happening Cyber Crime and Breach of Privacy	Bidisha Borah, 2020 Smagulov, S & Smagulov, V 2019
Return on Investment (ROI)	Digital services are mainly a cost factor	Smagulov, S & Smagulov, V 2019

5. Conclusion

The concept of Digital India is vast and wide. The main intention of this program is to improve the technical consciousness of people and to make them digitally literate. The digitalization of health care sector is very transparent and become close to people. It is resolving the problems by creating awareness among the people, maximizing internet connectivity, improving skills in cyber security, etc. Moreover, the Healthcare companies must develop a clear road of how they will match the digital needs of their customers, determine goals against this vision, and then commence with the implementation of digitalization system effectively and efficiently. The

health care sector in India is good but not sufficient. Information technology has not been introduced to improve its quality, affordability and accessibility of services to the mass people. To achieve this, the process of digitalization system should be carried out by starting with the investing in upgrading outdated technical systems and ending with the real time solutions to the problems at less cost and make them available in remote areas. Despite of the challenges faced in digital transformation of healthcare sector in India, the Government should develop policy guidelines and promote digital health and wellness initiatives to monitor, align, and supervise the digitalization system.

Acknowledgement

Venkatesh Bathala is the awardee of ICSSR Doctoral Fellow. This paper is largely an outcome of the Doctoral Fellowship sponsored by the Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR), New Delhi, India. However, the responsibility for the facts stated, opinions expressed, and the conclusions drawn is entirely of the author.

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